

**Kidnapping and Policy Inefficiency on Kidnapping Cases:
A Study of Ondo State, Nigeria**

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Abstract:

Technically, public policy is a primary political instrument. The inefficiency of the security policy has made it terribly fail in ensuring desirable internal security administration in Nigeria. In Ondo State, there is rampant kidnapping particularly in Akoko axis, including kidnapping/killing of Monarchs, creating immense fear and challenging traditional authority. The criminal gangs often kidnapers, bandits or herders use the terrain for ambushes and establishing camps which in turn deeply impact communities, disrupting farming which is a key sector in Ondo state, scare away investors, cripple tourism and force businesses to close thereby stalling Ondo development. Therefore, the paper examined kidnapping and policy inefficiency in kidnapping cases with a focus on Ondo State, in southwest Nigeria. The uprising kidnapping in Nigeria is calling for urgent attention. Despite the incessant kidnapping crime in Nigeria, there is no policy efficiency to reduce, end or ameliorate the problem in Nigeria even though there is a provision for it within Nigeria's legal framework. This study employs qualitative method and utilised secondary data sourced from books, journal articles, magazines, published reports, newspaper articles, and relevant Internet materials. However, the paper discovered that kidnapping and policy inefficiency on kidnapping cases and in addressing the menace in Nigeria are major impediments to security, economy and human development. The paper concludes that to reduce and ameliorate kidnapping, the government at all levels should collaborate and engage with experts to train stakeholders who could help to ensure the realisation of the security policies of the government, especially on kidnapping. The paper also advocated that it is necessary and high time kidnapping victims' right within the state's administration of criminal justice be recognised and legislated upon. It is pertinent that the government should provide a tending environment that propagates, strengthens and supports policy efficiency in addressing kidnapping cases to achieve economic growth, human development, and good governance and reduce incessant kidnapping.

Keywords: Kidnapping, Policy Inefficiency, Ondo State, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Kidnapping has remained an ongoing violent conflict globally, especially in developing countries, thereby impeding the path to peace and achieving justice and development (Welsh, 2024; Mbam et al., 2024; Jacinta, 2024; Gomez, 2024). Generally, the state's primary responsibility is the protection of the life and property of citizens (Fleming, 2020; Azimov, 2022; Tiwari, 2022). Social Contract theorists of state evolution argue that the need for security and protection from violence led citizens to give up their natural freedom in exchange for greater safety provided by the state (Gais, 2021; Ribarević, 2023; Wahlrab, 2023). According to this perspective, the state's primary responsibility is to ensure the security of lives and property. Thus, countries consider national security, human and material, as a fundamental priority in governing society. Section 14(2) (b) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended, mandated the government to prioritise the security and welfare of the people. This is because the security of life and property plays a well-being of people living within the territory.

The primary responsibility of the government is to ensure the security of the lives and properties of its citizens to enhance their development. Importantly, the government is expected to be actively involved in addressing security issues throughout the country. This could be achieved through policy efficiency in addressing the menace of incessant kidnapping across the country. This revolves around the relevance of policy efficiency in addressing kidnapping cases to achieve peace and development in Nigeria. However, for more than two decades, Nigeria has been embroiled in a cycle of recurring insecurity challenges, ranging from kidnapping, terrorism, ritual killing, Fulani herdsmen attacks, armed robbery, political violence, cultism, thuggery, banditry, ISWAP and Boko Haram insurgencies, to unknown gunmen who have constituted obstacles to economic growth and development (Akingbade, 2022).

Properties of monumental worth have been destroyed, while many people have been displaced. It was reported by the Nigeria Bureau of statistics (NBS 2024) that between May, 2023 and April, 2024, Nigerians paid over N2.2 trillion as ransom. It was reported that the average amount paid as ransom for kidnapping was N2.7 million per incident, (NBS 2024). Also, SB Morgen Intelligence reported that N2.57 billion was paid as ransom between July 2024 and June 2025. According to the National Human Right Commission (2025), 278 cases of kidnapping were reported in April, 2025 alone. Many businesses have been closed, thereby hindering the socio-economic prospects of citizens and the broader society.

However, the policy inefficiency in tackling the incessant kidnapping has made people continue to live in fear. Ordinarily, people should be free of fear from all forms of violence and feel safe as they go about their lives, whatever their ethnicity, faith, or sexual orientation. Kidnapping, as well as other criminal restiveness, started initially as part of the methods used by the Niger Delta militants to attract the attention of oil companies and the government to their struggle for resource control (Fagbadebo & Akinola, 2010; Fagbadebo, 2010). Kidnapping then created the impression that the lives of oil workers, prominent citizens and ordinary Nigerians were not safe, thereby portraying the image of

an insecure nation in the global system, with its attendant consequences (Ikuomola, 2011).

The trauma experienced by kidnapping victims extends beyond physical harm, with psychological consequences often lingering long after the event. As noted by Tade and Olaitan (2024), victims of criminal activities like kidnapping experience severe emotional distress, including PTSD, insomnia, and hyper vigilance. These experiences are compounded by the financial strain on victims' families, who are often forced to sell their assets or take loans to pay the demanded ransom by the kidnappers. Mmahi et al. (2022) further examine and noted the broader economic implications of kidnapping for ransom, arguing that, it has a negative impact on foreign investment in Nigeria, as potential investors view the rising insecurity as a significant risk factor. Despite efforts by both government and non-governmental organizations to curb the rise in kidnappings, the prevalence of these crimes continues to grow, underscoring the inadequacy of current security frameworks. It was also suggested by Oludare et al. (2021) that there is an urgent need for comprehensive interventions, including robust legal frameworks, improved law enforcement, and victim support systems to address the rising tide of insecurity in Nigeria. According to Porter et al. (2025) it is important to understand the lived experiences of victims of kidnappers in order to develop more effective strategies to ensure the safety of the people.

However, the criminal justice system of Nigeria is faced with challenges hindering deterrence and addressing the issue of kidnapping. This could be attributable to systemic inefficiencies prevailing within crucial institutions. Low prosecution rates, police corruption, and judiciary delays are major culprits and sadly highlight how Nigeria's criminal justice apathy and inefficiency engendered kidnapping in Nigeria. Ultimately, the low Prosecution rates of perpetrators of kidnapping disable the punitive function of the Law. In 2018, a Statista report documented that, there were about 838 reported cases of kidnapping, and 176 of the cases charged to court and 140 under investigation, only in 2018 (Statista, 2018). This attitude of sloppy enforcement not only emboldens and or strengthened criminal networks but also incentivises youth participation in such illicit activities due to the minimal risk of apprehension or prosecution (Eze & Nnaji, 2021).

The heighten security vacuum persists due to weak coordination, underfunding, and corruption in the police force, which allows perpetrators to go unchecked. As noted by Eze and Nnaji (2021), the weakness of law enforcement institutions, particularly in rural communities with limited governmental oversight, fosters conditions under which kidnapping can flourish. Nevertheless, weapons of kidnapping, as well as other measures that engendered insecurity, became established and entrenched instruments of violence and criminal activities that redefined the phase of insecurity in Nigeria (Oladoyin et al. 2024). As the socio-economic and political environment of the country became increasingly unstable and inhospitable for survival, criminal elements exploited vulnerable situations to resort to a series of measures that heightened the tempo of insecurity, thereby hindering meaningful growth for sustainable development.

Given the complexity and gravity of the kidnapping problem, particularly along the Akure, Akoko and Owo in Ondo State, this study aims to explore the causes, prevalence, and consequences of kidnapping on the citizens. The study will also assess the effectiveness of public policy and current preventive measures, providing a comprehensive analysis that contributes to the ongoing discourse on the impact of kidnapping on public safety, socio-economic stability, and national security in Nigeria.

1.1 Ondo state

Ondo State was created in 1976 out of the former Western State. The state lies between latitudes 5°45' and 7°52'N and longitudes 4°20' and 6°03'E. It is bounded on the east by Edo and Delta States, on the west by Ogun and Osun States, on the north by Ekiti and Kogi States, and to the south by the Bight of Benin of the Atlantic Ocean. The state occupies a land area of about 15,000 Square kilometers with a population of 3,441,924 people according to the 2006 census. However, the state has eighteen (18) Local Government Areas, with Akure as the capital city as well as the largest settlement. Some of the other prominent towns in the state are Ondo, Owo, Ore, Okitipupa, Ikare, Idanre, and Ile-Oluji. The people of the state are mostly Yoruba, although other Nigerians and foreign nationals also live in the state. It is important to note that Agriculture is the mainstay of the people of Ondo State. The state has notable tourist attractions which include Owo Museum, Ipale Iloro Water Falls, Igbokoda Water Front, Oke Maria Hills and Olumirin Water Fall, among others.

However, the structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2, Statement of the Problem. Section 3, Kidnapping in Nigeria and Section 4 will be an analysis of the Economy: A factor breeding kidnapping in Nigeria. Therefore, Section 5 addresses the insecure forest as an avenue for criminality, violence and kidnapping in Nigeria. Also, Section 6 will be on Public Policy on Kidnapping in Nigeria, with a focus on Ondo State. Section 7 Present the Conclusion while Section 8 will present the Recommendations.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Generally, Nigeria for years was one of the countries that are relatively peaceful in the world with socio-economic prospects. It is frightening and distressing to know the state downgraded as one of the most insecure places to live in the world, particularly during an economic downturn. It is evident that the security challenges in Nigeria, particularly kidnapping, have continued to threaten not only the survival of the nation but also international security as well. However, human and material costs of conflict are enormous and far-reaching with serious negative repercussions on the people and national economy. As the living standard of Nigerian people declined due to socio-economic downturn, the struggle for survival exacerbated, and Nigeria became the breeding ground for all manner of criminal activities, particularly incessant kidnapping. The failure of the government to keep the promises of adequate security of life and property, policy inefficiency to address the menace and socio-economic advancement have built up the feelings of frustration in the minds of the people (Ikelegbe 2006).

Therefore, it has created a large class of young men and women who have no hopes for legitimate employment opportunities that would fulfil their ambition. Thus, they are easily recruited into violent activities such as kidnapping. The significance of policy efficiency in addressing insecurity, such as kidnapping, and in improving peaceful co-existence and stimulating a conducive environment for viable social-economic activities to thrive should be recognised by successive Nigerian governments. It is against this background that the study seeks to address kidnapping and the policy inefficiency in kidnapping cases in Nigeria, drawing insights from Ondo State.

2. KIDNAPPING AND INCIDENTS OF KIDNAPPING IN NIGERIA

Various scholars have defined kidnapping, Inyang and Abraham (2013) described it as “the forcible seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his or her will. It is a common law offence, and the key part is that it is an unwanted act on the part of the victim”. Fage and Alabi (2017) conceived kidnapping as “forceful or fraudulent abduction of an individual or a group of individuals for reasons ranging from economic, political, and religious to [struggle for] self-determination”. However, the authors later admitted that forcefully or fraudulently abducted individuals are carried off as hostages for ransom purposes. This implies that while political and economic factors can instigate kidnapping, the financial reason is the most common predisposing factor of the phenomenon. Kidnapping is on the increase in Nigeria. Statistically, Nigeria records more than 1,000 kidnapping incidents a year, and there are undoubtedly many that are unreported (Agbaje, 2022).

Kidnapping has become a significant crime in Nigeria of late; it is a national problem that has resulted not only in the loss of money, through the paying of ransoms, but also in several cases in the rape and murder of the victims. A vast number of kidnappers operate from thick forests where they keep their victims for ransom and/or rape. For instance, in April 2013, a school boy was kidnapped and kept in a forest at Olorunlekan village in Oja Odan in Ogun State (Daily Post, 2013). Also, on 23 August 2013, Mike Ozekhome, a senior lawyer in Nigeria, was abducted by kidnappers and taken to a thick forest located between Benin and Auchu in Edo State, where he, along with one of the lawyers in his chamber, spent 20 days before being rescued by the police (Vanguard Newspaper, 2013).

In May 2015, it took the combined efforts of the Nigerian police and local hunters to rescue 11 people (mostly lecturers and nurses) who had been kidnapped and were being kept in a dense forest located in Esure, a town in the Irepodun/Ifelodun local government area of Ekiti State (Guardian Newspaper, 2015). In the same vein, the Ekiti State Commissioner of Police, Wilson Inalegwu, confirmed that forests along the Ise-Emure and Ikere-Igbara Odo roads serve as bases for kidnappers (Punch Newspaper, 2017).

On 14th April 2016, a reporter with Channels TV, Eyitope Kuteyi recounted how he spent two nights at the kidnappers’ den located in the heart of Uhuba Forest in the Uhaji Egbema local government area of Imo State, (The Nation Newspaper, 2016). In the

same April 2016, security operatives discovered 55 graves containing victims of kidnapping and abductions in Umuanyi Forest in Abia State (The Punch Newspaper, 2016 & Channels TV, 2016). In November 2016, the Administrative Secretary of the Independent National Electoral Commission in Ekiti State, Dr Muslim Omoleke, was kidnapped along with his son and driver by a gang operating from a forest around Ilesha in Osun State (Vanguard newspaper, 4th November 2016). Between 27 November and 3 December 2016, the police arrested three kidnapers at their hideouts in the Epe and Ajase-Ipo forests who were responsible for the abduction of a Dangote company worker (Vanguard Newspaper, 2016). Also, on 10th December 2016, two people were rescued from Buzun Forest by members of the police and Danga Security, a local vigilante group (Tribune Newspaper, 2016). On 6th December 2016, the police in Enugu State rescued an 18-year-old woman from a kidnapper's den located in Ugbawka Forest in the Nkanu East local government area (Vanguard Newspaper, 2016). On 2 March 2017, Henry Chibueze (aka Vampire), the leader of what has been described as the deadliest kidnapping gang in south-eastern Nigeria, was killed during a gun battle with the police in his hideout located inside a forest in Omu Awa in the Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State (Vanguard Newspaper, 2017).

Criminals operating in a complex syndicate have also exploited the thick forestland between Abuja and Kaduna. Victims are abducted on the highway and taken into the inner recesses of the forest. However, in 2022, Vanguard newspaper reported that one of the victims narrated the experience thus: They turned to me and ordered me to follow them. They also asked the driver to do the same. Our abductors eventually took us hostage and, after riding us on motorcycles for more than an hour, they took us to one of their heavily guarded camps, deep in the forest, where they vowed not to release us until millions of naira had been paid ransom (Vanguard Newspaper, 2022).

Furthermore, Kamuku Forest, bordering the states of Kaduna, Katsina, Niger, Kebbi and Zamfara, is regarded as one of the deadliest forests in the country on account of its usage for criminal ends by people who specialise in kidnapping for ransom and raping women (Ibrahim & Ahmad, 2020). In Kano, Falgore and Gomo, forests have also become a nightmare for residents of the Doguwa, Sumaila, Tudun Wada, and Kibiya communities, due to the high rates of kidnapping perpetrated by individuals operating from deep within the forests (Daily Trust, July 29, 2017). The International Centre for Investigative Reporting in Abuja reported the rescue of 11 victims of kidnapping from the Falgore forest (Global Forest Watch 2015).

In Bauchi State, forests such as Yuga and Lame-Burra in the Toro Local Government Area, Balmo in the Darazo Local Government Area, Buzun in the Ganjuwa Local Government Area, and Yankari in the Alkaleri Local Government Area are classified as havens for kidnapers (Daily Trust, March 13, 2022). Ogere Forest in Ibadan also serves as a kidnapers' den, and it is here that a 52-year-old businesswoman was kept for two days after being abducted, before being rescued (Atoyebi, 2017). Also, Kidnap victims are kept in the forest located at the Benin City bypass in Edo State, which is also where

ransom is dropped; failure to do so results in victims being murdered (Vanguard Newspaper, 19th May 2013).

3. ECONOMY: A FACTOR BREEDING KIDNAPPING IN NIGERIA

Notably, economic deprivation and a sense of desperation have planted the seeds of kidnapping as a way of getting money in poor communities. It can then become a way of life, even when legal options become available (Catlin Group, 2012). The disparity between the rich and the poor is growing, and the internet and global media make everyone see how the rich are living. It fuels resentment and a desire for a bigger share (Catlin Group, 2012). Over the last twenty years, individuals have constructed fortifications to ensure the safety and protection of their dwellings (Adedeji et al., 2022). However, the vast sum of money and other booty procured from kidnapped persons or families amidst severe economic asperities serve as a core promulgating factor of kidnapping in the country. It also provides strong incentives for continuity and the desire of most kidnapers to stay in the illicit business indefinitely. Research has shown that kidnapping is likely to increase in countries with poorly performing economies and during economic downturns (Roberts, 2017; Ibrahim & Ahmad, 2020). The financial dilemma in which Nigeria is currently entrapped has created a fertile ground for the emergence and growth of various criminal activities, including kidnapping. However, it is instructive to note that economic growth cannot be achieved without securing socio-economic activities to stimulate it (Omoredede, 2023).

Although Nigeria is richly endowed with both human its and natural resources, many of citizens (especially the youth) still wallow in abject poverty (Aleyomi & Olajubu, 2024; Abati, 2009). This has left many perplexed and wondering if Nigeria is truly the giant of Africa, as often propagated in the media. Despite its enormous cultivable land and numerous oil wells, the country paradoxically remains largely underdeveloped, and many of its citizens are impoverished (Agbaje, 2022; Osumah & Aghedo, 2011). Recent findings indicate that approximately 46% of the Nigerian population lives below the poverty line (Alfred et al., 2014; Fagbamigbe et al., 2021). That is, about 70 million Nigerians live below the poverty line, with an average income of about US\$1 per day (Fagbamigbe et al., 2021; Alfred et al., 2014; Abati, 2009).

Generally, unemployment is very high in Nigeria. Many youths in Nigeria are unemployed (Imhonopi et al., 2016). Sadly, Nigeria's unemployment problem is compounded by increased nepotism and job racketeering. Unlike the experience in developed Western societies, and relatively in some African societies where recruitment processes are fair and excellence is rewarded, recruitment processes for most jobs in Nigeria are often fraudulent and rooted in corrupt practices (Agbaje, 2022; Imhonopi et al., 2016).

Recruitment in Nigeria is often like a process that favors the highest bidder (i.e., based on a strong connection). Suppose you do not belong to the aristocratic class or are related to a highly placed politician or influential personality in society. In that case, your chances of securing a befitting job in Nigeria are relatively slim. Therefore, academic prowess plays a minimal role in generating promising job opportunities for most youths in Nigeria (Imhonopi et al., 2016; Oluwaniyi, 2011). Currently, many educated youths are roaming the streets with qualifications that are commensurate with job opportunities.

Moreover, since most of them have been excluded from public space owing to unemployment, many have now carved out a social space for themselves in a marginal environment to commit crimes (including kidnapping), a culture that is resistant to the dominant or mainstream culture (Abati, 2009; Diouf, 2003; Osumah & Aghedo, 2011).

As a result of the rise unemployment in Nigeria, this has led to the youths engaging in various social crimes, such banditry and kidnapping. The increase in idle labour as a result of unemployed youth has led to increase in youth vulnerability to criminal ventures. The marginalisation of the Youth has also led to rise in resentment and quest for alternative income through kidnapping-for-ransom (Mbam et al., 2024). Inyang (2019) argued that the growing incidence of kidnapping is as a result of the structural problem of youth unemployment, illustrating the issue through the widely cited aphorism, “an idle man is the devil’s workshop,” which encapsulates the social risks associated with mass idleness. Similarly, Linus (2015) highlights the alarming reality of numerous physically capable young Nigerians who remain unemployed, constantly searching for non-existent job opportunities.

According to (Mbam et al., 2024); Ayuba (2020), (Yusuf & Abdulahhi, 2020) in an empirical investigation into the underlying causes of kidnapping, it was found that the surge in kidnapping incidents is largely attributable to limited employment opportunities for young people. A significant proportion of these youths have disengaged from agriculture, the region’s traditional economic base and migrated to urban centers in pursuit of largely unavailable jobs. Many of the youth, after being used as political thugs for election campaigns and subsequently abandoned by their political sponsors, resort to kidnapping as an alternative means of survival (Ayuba, 2020). Hence, the proliferation of kidnapping in Nigeria is not unexpected (Abati, 2009).

4. INSECURE FORESTS AS A CATALYST FOR CRIMINALITY, VIOLENCE AND KIDNAPPING

Generally, in Nigeria, it is evident that humans have long exploited forests as both cover from which to launch attacks and as a defence against them during wars and invasions. Thus, its usage is often double-edged, for both defence and offence. In Nigeria, however, the negative exploitation of forests has gained more prominence, and there is increasing evidence of forest spaces being used to facilitate violent criminal acts, kidnapping, insurgencies, rebel movements, armed robberies, illegal logging, illicit drug cultivation and outlawed trading. Recent studies show that at least half of the violent conflicts of the twentieth century took place in forested areas, such as in Ethiopia, Colombia, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), India, Liberia, Mexico, Myanmar, the Philippines, Nepal, Uganda, Sri Lanka and of course Nigeria. Due to how they offer shelter from government forces, insurgents and rebels have repeatedly used forests as places of refuge and a means of fuelling their activities and illicit trade (Agbaje, 2022).

Forests have been used by insurgents in Nigeria to perpetrate their violent activities against the state. Boko Haram insurgents are notorious in this regard, operating from some forests in north-eastern Nigeria, including the Sambisa, Kala Balje, Balmo and Kagoro forests. Sambisa Forest sprawls across a vast area, bordering Borno, Yobe, Bauchi, and Kano states, and extending to the neighbouring countries of Cameroon, Niger, and Chad. Its vastness, rugged terrain, sparse population and dense tree cover make

surveillance difficult, thereby making it an ideal hiding place for Boko Haram militants. Sambisa is a government-protected forest rich in wildlife and offers numerous prospects for tourism. On the 5th of February 2013, Boko Haram insurgents invaded the forest, killed two government workers and subsequently annexed the forest as its headquarters. Insurgents then made the inner recesses of the forest not only their main arena of operation but also the place they retreated to after engaging in attacks on civilians in neighbouring towns and villages in Nigeria.

The conquest of the Sambisa Forest afforded the group an easy entrance for seizing territory in the mainland areas of north-east Nigeria and establishing its form of government in an area as large as Belgium. Serving as the headquarters of the group, the forests provide ample space in which to keep the hostages that are abducted, including the many women and underage girls who are used as sex slaves and suicide bombers. The most widely reported incident in the series of such burdens is that of the schoolgirls who were kidnapped from their school dormitory in Chibok in 2014.

In the same vein, Burra Forest in the Ningi local government area of Bauchi State also serves as a hideout for Boko Haram insurgents. The forest is a corridor linking the Falgore and Saminaka forests in Kano and Kaduna states, respectively. Some of the Boko Haram members relocated to this forest when the state's military started bombarding Sambisa Forest. They use the sanctuary of the forest to engage in kidnapping for ransom and the killing of civilians, and they also engage in vicious attacks on security forces, as well as the tourists visiting the Yankari National Park. Nevertheless, Kala-Balge Forest has served as one of the campsites of the militants, from which they launched an unsuccessful attack on Kala/Balge village on 14 May 2014.

A revenge mission was orchestrated on the Kala/Balge local government area from the same forest base on 31 May 2014, which resulted in the death of 40 people, 65 and it was to the same forest that group leader Abubakar Shekarau retreated after he was dislodged from Sambisa. In another instance, Balmo Forest in Bauchi served as one of the strongholds of the group and has even served as an armoury for Boko Haram groups, as evidenced by the discovery of a huge stock of weapons during army raids on 5 and 6 July 2014. In addition, Boko Haram rebels also maintain camps in Galda Forest in Gombe, from which they launch frequent attacks on residents of the city, the most vicious being on 14 February 2015, when the whole town was invaded, and several people were killed. Specifically, there is a lack, or inadequacy, of state presence in several forests. This absence has led to the emergence of violent forces that have successfully converted forest spaces for their own activities and interests. In other words, the invasion and conversion of forests for bases of operation from which to conduct criminal activity highlights the absence of the state in these spaces, showing forest spaces to be ungoverned at various points in time and used as an avenue for various attacks on citizens, which in turn affect the socioeconomic advancement.

5. PUBLIC POLICY ON KIDNAPPING IN NIGERIA

There is a clear indication of the government's interest in and commitment to increasing the security of lives and properties in order to provide a peaceful society in Nigeria. The

clarity of this is evident in Section 364 of the Criminal Code Act in Nigeria, which states that, any person who-

- (1) Unlawfully imprisons any person, and takes him out of Nigeria without his consent; or
- (2) Unlawfully imprisons any person within Nigeria in such a manner as to prevent him from applying to a court for his release or from discovering to any other person the place where he is imprisoned, or in such a manner as to prevent any person entitled to have access to him from discovering the place where he is imprisoned, is guilty of a felony and is liable to imprisonment for ten years.

It should be noted that there is a law on kidnapping in Nigeria. Therefore, the various states' Houses of Assembly possess the powers to enact laws on kidnapping. In line with that, some state Houses of Assembly have enacted laws on kidnapping in their states. In 2009, kidnapping was made a capital offence in six different states in Nigeria, which include: Imo, Anambra, Abia, Akwa-Ibom, Enugu, and Ebonyi states. Similarly, in 2010, Kwara State enacted the Kwara State Prohibition and Kidnapping Law 2010. In the same year, Kogi State also passed "The Kogi State Kidnapping, Thuggery and other Related Offences Prohibition law, 2010". In 2013, it is evident that Seriake Dickson, the Governor of Bayelsa State, was one of the governors in the Niger Delta region who approved the death penalty for kidnapping cases. Also, in Edo State, Comrade Adams Oshiomhole also approved capital punishment for kidnapping in 2013, which imposed the death penalty in the state, and it applies to all acts of kidnapping, whether it involved murder or not. In the same vein, the Delta State House of Assembly also passed into law the Anti-Kidnapping Bill 2013, which imposes a death sentence on any person convicted of kidnapping in the state.

It was noted by Ezugwu (2017) that because of the ravaging epidemic of kidnapping for ransom, state governors called for tougher sanctions or laws that would put a stop to abduction. In Rivers State, Rivers State, which has been feeling the heat of abduction, was the first to advocate for the death penalty before other states. Enugu State, therefore, followed suit. Already, the Rivers State House of Assembly has passed the prohibition of kidnapping law of the state, making kidnapping an offence punishable by life imprisonment. Enugu State House of Assembly went further to make kidnapping an offence punishable by death. And in the case of abduction without a gun, the offence attracts 10 years imprisonment (Ezeaku, 2016).

In the same vein, Oyo state assented to a new kidnapping (prohibition) bill 2016, which prescribes a death sentence or life imprisonment for any person who engages in kidnapping. According to the Oyo State kidnapping law, any kidnapper whose victim or victims die while in captivity will be liable to capital punishment. In contrast, a convicted offender whose victim is released or rescued unharmed upon the payment of a ransom will

be liable to life imprisonment and be compelled to pay back the ransom. The Oyo State law further prescribes various punishments for any person who threatens to kill, maim or cause bodily harm in order to compel another person, corporate body or organisation to do or obtain from doing any act as a condition for the release of the victim. Similarly, anyone who attempts to kidnap, aids or abets kidnapping will be sentenced to not less than 15 years imprisonment.

In 2010, the Ondo State House of Assembly enacted the “Ondo State Anti-Kidnapping and Anti-Abduction Law” to provide appropriate punishment for the Act of kidnapping and Abduction in Ondo State. The law was passed in 2010 as a reaction to the public outcry to the increased spate of kidnapping in Ondo State. According to the law, “kidnap or abduct include unlawful removal or exportation of a person from any place where he or she is, to another place from the vicinity where he or she is found, or the unlawful confinement of a person in any place without his or her consent with any of the following intentions or purposes; to hold for ransom or reward, a shield or hostage, to facilitate the commission of a felony, to inflict bodily injury on or terrorize the victim or another, to interfere with the performance of any Governmental or Political function, to interfere with the person’s business or business of another”.

It was stated that, “any person who take as hostage, captures, kidnaps, abducts, seizes, a person or by any means of instilling fear, tricks, carries, snatches or takes another person with intent to demand ransom from that person or from another person or to compel another to do anything against his will or achieve an unlawful purpose commit an offence”. However, any person who contravenes this law, where the life of the person taken hostage, captured, carried, snatched, kidnapped, abducted or seized is lost in the process, shall be liable for conviction to death by hanging. But, where the life of the person taken hostage, captured, carried, snatched, kidnapped, abducted or seized is not lost in the process, shall be liable for conviction to life imprisonment without an option of fine. Also, the Ondo State Anti-Kidnapping and Anti-Abduction Law stated that any person who attempts to commit any act of taking hostage, capturing, snatching, kidnapping or abducting commits an offence and is liable on conviction to 20 years imprisonment without an option of fine.

In 2017, the Senate passed a bill which penalizes abduction, wrongful restraint or confinement for ransom. The Senate of the Federal Republic of Nigeria approved a death sentence for whoever engages in the act and a 30-year jail term for anybody who colludes with an abductor. The bill in Clause 1 (3) stated: “Whoever is guilty of the offence and then results in the death of the victim shall be liable on conviction to be sentenced to death.” Clause 3 of the bill, a 30-year jail term is provided to anyone who colludes with an abductor to receive any ransom for the release of a person who has been wrongfully confined (Busari, 2017). Despite the government’s anti-graft war and laws, government contracting remains fraught with corruption and setbacks, and many states, including Ondo state, remain rife with corruption and inefficiencies in enforcing public policies on

kidnapping cases in Nigeria. Official enforcement and corruption are weak and ineffective, allowing the policies to be undermined.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper took a look at the problem of kidnapping as well as the policy inefficiency in kidnapping cases with a focus on Ondo State. The paper found out that kidnapping is a social scourge in the country with policy inefficiency to stem its tide. The bad economic situation also contributes to the increase in kidnapping, and the insecure forest is an avenue for conflict, violence and kidnapping in Nigeria. However, there was an attempt by Ondo State to use legislative instruments to control, bring it to a halt or at least reduce its occurrence within the state. Critically, looking at the Ondo State Anti-kidnapping and Anti-Abduction Law, 2010, it should be noted that the law merely recognised a victim of kidnapping without making any provision for any form of compensation or any restitution for the victim of kidnapping.

The paper therefore recommends that:

- In order to reduce and ameliorate kidnapping, the government at all levels should collaborate and engage with experts to train stakeholders who could help to ensure the realisation of the security policies of the government, especially regarding kidnapping.
- Collectively, we can rid Nigeria of kidnapping or reduce the operation to the barest minimum by providing information that will enable the police and other security agencies to apprehend the culprit. In developed countries, the citizens help the security agencies with accurate information in reducing crime, which can be replicated in Nigeria. There is a need for police and other security agencies to build the confidence of the people in doling out helpful information to curb crimes, especially kidnapping. Kidnappers are not spirits, but human beings with hardened minds who are getting back at society for their perceived grievances and inability to make a livelihood.
- It is advocated that it is necessary and high time that kidnapping victims' rights within the state's administration of criminal justice be recognised and passed into law.
- The government should ensure that the resources of the country are harnessed for national development and in promoting national prosperity. The government has a responsibility to protect the lives and properties of the citizens and to secure Nigeria.
- Policy on sanctions directed at kidnapping should be efficient, enforced and should be approached both coolly and dispassionately. Criminologist Walker (2006) explained that many crime policies are unrelated to the most serious part of the crime problem.
- The government should partner with private investors to boost security in the country.

- Finally, the security agencies must collaborate with community leaders to monitor the activities of criminals in all flashpoint areas and identify their hideouts. This way, the bad eggs can be easily fished out.

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